

Antibiotic Stewardship Awareness Among Multidisciplinary Student Cohorts: A KAP Study

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Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR), driven by antibiotic misuse and overuse, is a major global health threat. Assessing students' knowledge, awareness, and practices (KAP) is vital for promoting antibiotic stewardship. This study evaluates and compares KAP on antibiotic use and AMR among health-allied and non-health-allied students, while identifying demographic predictors influencing KAP scores to guide targeted interventions. A cross-sectional, questionnaire-based online survey was conducted among 236 students of JIS University between October 2024 and April 2025. The validated questionnaire comprised demographic items and KAP domains. Reliability was confirmed via Cronbach's alpha (Knowledge = 0.710, Awareness = 0.905, Practice = 0.741), and KMO and Bartlett's tests confirmed sampling adequacy. Statistical analysis included Mann-Whitney U test, Pearson's correlation, and multiple regression using SPSS version 20. Health-allied students exhibited significantly higher KAP scores than non-health counterparts ($p < 0.001$). Gender and field of study significantly influenced knowledge scores; education level and field of study impacted awareness and practice scores. Age showed no significant association with any domain. Positive correlations were found between all KAP components. These findings underscore the need for targeted, discipline-specific awareness campaigns and curricula to promote rational antibiotic use and curb AMR.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Awareness, Cross-sectional study, Knowledge, Practices

Introduction

Antibiotics- one of the greatest discoveries of 20th century in the history of medicines have played a crucial role of curing infectious disease and saving countless lives. Unfortunately, these lifesaving drugs are becoming increasingly ineffective. Diseases that were once easily treated are now becoming virtually untreatable. This alarming trend is primarily due to overuse, misuse and irrational use of antibiotics. Other contributing factors include unregulated drug availability, procurement of antibiotics without prescription (Over-the-counter), insufficient public awareness, and attitude towards antibiotic consumption. The consequence of irrational use of antibiotics has resulted in antibiotic resistance which is a serious threat to the entire world today.[1-3]

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a silent pandemic which adversely impacts patient care threatens return to pre-antibiotic era, jeopardises healthcare gains to society with increase in both direct and indirect economic costs, morbidity, mortality in both hospital and simple community-acquired infections. The rise of antibiotic-resistant bacteria has led to a global public health crisis.[4,5]

Recent research has increasingly addressed antibiotic misuse and KAP related to antimicrobial use across various populations.[6,7] However, in India, well-structured studies assessing KAP—especially among students from both health-allied and non-health disciplines—are limited. This study seeks to fill this gap by evaluating and comparing KAP on antibiotic use and AMR among diverse student groups, and identifying demographic factors influencing these outcomes, to support rational antibiotic use.

Methodology

Study design

A cross-sectional questionnaire-based online survey

Target study population

The target study population included students of JIS University from varied academic backgrounds.

Study duration

The research was conducted between October 2024 and April 2025 for a period of six months.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The study's inclusion criteria included males and female students who studied at JIS University, as well as students' who voluntarily participated in the study. Exclusion criteria included a refusal to participate in the study and failure to complete the assigned questionnaires through the survey conducted.

Validation of the study questionnaire

The study questionnaire was developed after reviewing relevant literature and was structured into four domains: demographics, knowledge, awareness, and practice. A pilot study involving 48 respondents was conducted to assess the reliability and appropriateness of the questionnaire. Internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, with initial scores of 0.636 (knowledge), 0.905 (awareness), and 0.741 (practice). After removing one knowledge-based question, the Cronbach's alpha improved to 0.710 for the knowledge section, while awareness and practice remained at 0.905 and 0.741 respectively, indicating acceptable to excellent reliability.[8] The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) values for knowledge (0.849), awareness (0.916), and

practice (0.797) confirmed meritorious to excellent sampling adequacy. Bartlett's tests of sphericity were significant ($p < 0.001$) for all domains, supporting the suitability of data for factor analysis.[9] The finalized questionnaire, hosted on Google Forms, included study details, assurances of anonymity and confidentiality, and emphasized voluntary participation. It was disseminated among students via various social media platforms.

Knowledge Awareness and Practice (KAP) Score

- Knowledge score (KS): Each correct answer was awarded 2 points; incorrect answers received 0. Scores were categorized as:
 - Low (0–6) • Moderate (7–13) • Good (14–20)
- Awareness score (AS): Based on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = least favorable, 5 = most favorable).
 - Low (14–32) • Moderate (33–51) • Good (52–70)
- Practice score (PS): Also rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = least desirable, 5 = most desirable)
 - Undesirable (14–32) • Neutral (33–51) • Desirable (52–70)

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki and was supported by the Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, JIS University, Kolkata. As it involved a voluntary, anonymous online KAP survey with no physical or psychological risk, and focused solely on student perceptions, formal ethical approval was waived.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The Mann–Whitney U test assessed group differences, while correlation analysis explored associations between demographics and KAP variables. Multiple regression identified sociodemographic predictors of KAP scores.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants

A total of 236 participants successfully completed the survey. Table 1 summarizes the socio-demographic characteristics of the study population. The average age of the study participants was 21.69 ± 0.21 years (median- 21 years, mode- 22 years). The age of 121 (51.27%) students was 21 years or below, whereas 115 (48.73%) students was above 21 years (Table 1).

The male participants in the study included 55.51% (131), whereas 44.49% (105) were females (Table 1). The majority of participants (86.86%, $n = 205$) were either enrolled in undergraduate programs or held an undergraduate degree, whereas only 13.14% ($n = 31$) were postgraduates (Table 1).

The online survey included students from diverse academic backgrounds, categorized into health-allied and non-health-allied fields to assess the impact of education on AMR perception. As shown in Table 1, 43.22% ($n=102$) were from health-allied disciplines (Pharmacy, Medical Lab Technology, Biosciences), while the remaining 134 students belonged to fields such as Law, Computer Science, and Education.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the study population

Factors	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age</i>		
<=21	121	51.27
>21	115	48.73
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	131	55.51
Female	105	44.49
<i>Level of Education</i>		
Undergraduate	205	86.86
Postgraduate	31	13.14
<i>Field of study</i>		
Health-allied field	102	43.22
Non-health allied field	134	56.78

KAP scores of the study participants

The study population had an average knowledge score of 13.95 ± 0.31 (range: 0–20), with 61.86% (n=146) securing high scores, indicating strong awareness of antibiotic use and AMR. The mean awareness score was 56.97 ± 0.6 (range: 14–70), with 75.84% (n=179) scoring high, reflecting acceptable comprehension of AMR-related health risks, while 23.73% (n=56) showed moderate awareness. The average practice score was 51.84 ± 0.55 (range: 14–70), with 54.66% (n=129) exhibiting neutral practices and 44.49% (n=105) demonstrating desirable antibiotic-related behaviors.

Association of socio-demographic variables with KAP scores

Table 2 presents the relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and KAP scores. The Mann–Whitney U test showed no significant association between age and any KAP domain ($p > 0.05$). However, gender was significantly associated with knowledge scores ($p < 0.05$), with females scoring higher than males, though no such association was observed for awareness or practice. Education level significantly influenced all three KAP scores ($p < 0.05$), with postgraduates scoring the highest. Field of study showed a highly significant association ($p < 0.001$), with students from health-allied disciplines achieving notably higher knowledge, awareness, and practice scores, indicating a positive impact of health-related education on AMR perception.

Table 2: Association between sociodemographic variables with KAP scores

Factors	Frequency	Percentage	KS	p value	AS	p value	PS	p value
<i>Age</i>								
≤21	121	51.27	13.98	0.87	56.53	0.34	52.13	0.655
>21	115	48.73	13.91		57.43		51.52	
<i>Gender</i>								
Male	131	55.51	13.34	0.036*	56.18	0.06	51.10	0.22
Female	105	44.49	14.70		57.94		52.75	
<i>Level of Education</i>								
Undergraduate	205	86.86	13.70	0.03*	56.32	0.01*	51.43	0.04*
Postgraduate	31	13.14	15.61		61.26		54.52	
<i>Field of study</i>								
Health-allied field	102	43.22	15.78	0.00**	58.86	0.00**	54.56	0.00**
Non-health allied field	134	56.78	12.55		55.52		49.76	

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01

Correlation between the KAP scores

Pearson correlation analysis revealed significant positive linear correlations between knowledge score and awareness score ($r=0.385$, $p<0.01$), knowledge score and practice score ($r=0.545$, $p<0.01$), and awareness score and practice score ($r=0.460$, $p<0.01$). These results confirm the interdependency of the students' knowledge, awareness, and practice levels (Figure 1). Therefore, the higher the knowledge level, the awareness is also improved and practices are also desirable.

Figure 1: Correlation analysis between the KAP scores as per Pearson correlation analysis (p<0.01)****Multiple regression analysis between the KAP scores**

The multiple regression analysis revealed that gender, level of education, and field of study significantly influenced KAP scores related to antimicrobial resistance. For knowledge, gender ($p=0.008$) and field of study ($p<0.001$) were significant predictors (Table 3). In the awareness domain, level of education ($p=0.029$) and field of study ($p=0.004$) showed significant associations. Regarding practice, both level of education ($p=0.037$) and field of study ($p<0.001$) were significant predictors. Age was not significantly associated with any of the KAP components. These findings highlight the impact of academic background and education on AMR-related knowledge, awareness, and practices.

Table 3: Multiple regression analysis between the KAP scores

Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	t	p
<i>Knowledge</i>				
Age	-.068	.651	-.993	.322
Gender	.162	.583	2.670	.008**
Level of education	.116	.580	1.700	.090
Field of study	-.346	.585	-5.690	.000**
<i>Awareness</i>				
Age	-.027	1.320	-.382	.703
Gender	.106	1.182	1.665	.097
Level of education	.157	1.176	2.200	.029*
Field of study	-.185	1.186	-2.900	.004**
<i>Practice</i>				
Age	-.109	1.187	-1.560	.120
Gender	.114	1.063	1.827	.069
Level of education	.146	1.057	2.093	.037*
Field of study	-.287	1.066	-4.622	.000**

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01

Discussion

Antimicrobial resistance is a global challenge for the entire medical fraternity that not only reduces the therapeutic efficacy but increases the risk of mortality of patients and, in turn, aggravates the medical costs. KAP surveys are essential to obtain a comprehensive assessment of the understanding, awareness and practice of the society towards the use of antibiotics and the severity of AMR.[10] The present study revealed that most of the study participants (86.86%) were undergraduate students. Socio-demographic features further confirmed that 48.22% of the subjects were from health-allied background and the rest from non-health-allied field. The average knowledge score of the participants was found to be relatively high, with more than 60% of students were under the 'good knowledge' category. Statistical analysis revealed that postgraduate students had a significantly higher score ($p<0.05$) compared to the undergraduates, whereas students from health-allied background had a highly significant ($p<0.01$) score compared to the non-health-allied field students. This suggests a strong conceptual understanding of antibiotics and AMR, that is in alliance to their curriculum and academic exposure. A multicentric study among Indian clinicians revealed satisfactory knowledge regarding AMR.[11] Another similar study among medical students claimed that more than 80% correctly responded to the knowledge-based questions.[12] Similar study among non-healthcare students revealed 55.2% had moderate knowledge score. Many participants were unaware of the correct use of antibiotics and the consequences of misuse. This article also emphasized the need for educational interventions among non-healthcare students to improve awareness and promote responsible antibiotic use.[13]

Awareness levels reported positive outcome with high score secured by 75.84% of the students. Mann-Whitney U test revealed the awareness scores were relatively higher ($p<0.05$) for the postgraduate and health-allied students. Interestingly, it was found that 25.37% of the students from non-health allied field responded either neutral or disagreed to the fact that self-medication of antibiotics can lead to AMR, whereas the count was 13.72% for the health-allied field. Also, 77.07% of the undergraduate students acknowledged that self-medication can lead to AMR. Among the respondents, 73.13% from non-health-allied

backgrounds and 85.29% from health-allied fields were aware of the importance of completing the full course of antibiotics, while 93.55% of postgraduates and 76.1% of undergraduates recognized that incomplete antibiotic use can lead to AMR. A total of 31.43% of students from non-health-allied backgrounds and 23.53% from health-allied fields, along with 30.73% of undergraduates and 9.68% of postgraduates, were unaware that antibiotics are ineffective against viral infections. These findings suggest that higher education level and healthcare-related academic exposure are positively associated with better understanding of antibiotic compliance and its role in preventing AMR. Similar study revealed that 35.6% of the participants agreed that non-completion of antibiotic course can lead to AMR.[14] In another study, 45.5% of the students opined that antibiotics have preventive potential in cough or sore throat.[13] These incomplete understanding and misconceptions can aggravate the risk of AMR. As awareness is critical to influencing behavior, enhancing communication around AMR through campaigns, peer education, and institutional seminars is imperative.

The practice scores revealed a contrasting trend. While knowledge and awareness levels were high, only 44.49% of students demonstrated desirable practices, with over half showing neutral behavior. Only 51.61% of postgraduate students and 39.51% of undergraduate students reported consulting a physician before taking antibiotics, while 29.03% of postgraduates, 39.51% of undergraduates, and 30.39% subjects from health-allied field admitted to often using leftover antibiotics from previous prescriptions. Present study revealed that statistics was also high for those who purchased antibiotics without proper prescriptions. Furthermore, 41.79% of participants from non-health-allied backgrounds admitted to extending or reducing the duration of their antibiotic course without proper medical advice. Such self-directed modifications in antibiotic use reflect poor awareness. This alarming trend highlights irrational antibiotic practices that can significantly contribute to the rise of AMR. This gap between knowledge and attitude and practice is consistent with findings from previous studies conducted on medical students in Jammu, India.[15] Moderate KAP scores were also reported among non-healthcare students in Zambia.[13]

Correlation analysis revealed significant positive associations among knowledge, awareness, and practice scores, indicating that enhanced knowledge can lead to greater awareness and improved behaviors. These findings highlight the potential of targeted educational interventions to foster responsible antibiotic use. The study addresses a critical gap by offering comparative insights into AMR perceptions across health-allied and non-health disciplines within a university context. It contributes to the limited interdisciplinary KAP literature in India and provides evidence to guide the development of tailored educational strategies based on demographic and academic factors.

Conclusion

This study reveals notable differences in antibiotic-related knowledge, awareness, and practices among students from various academic backgrounds, with health-allied students scoring significantly higher. The strong positive correlations between knowledge, awareness, and practices highlight the role of education in promoting responsible antibiotic use. These findings stress the urgent need for interdisciplinary AMR education to empower all students—future professionals and leaders—to combat antimicrobial resistance and protect public health.

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